

Energy Sustainable Water Fountain

Grøn Dyst - Fagprojekt 41801
In collaboration with Fokdal Springvand A/S

Focus on energy consumption

Beautiful, mystic, intriguing, entertaining etc.. Many of these words describe water fountains all around the world. Now we introduce new words to the vocabulary – green, energy sustainable and environmentally friendly. This poster demonstrates a way to reduce the power consumption of water fountains. This is an area that is traditionally neglected by designers.

How to reduce the power consumption?

The power consumption of a pump is proportional to the amount of water it transports. By making hollow water jets, it is possible to reduce the power consumption by more than 50%. This means huge energy savings when paired with fountains running throughout most of the day, every day, for the entire year.

Hollow water jets? But how??

Making a hollow water jet is significantly more difficult than solid ones. They are formed by an outer nozzle, shaping the exterior, and an inner, defining the width and angle of the water jet. Experiments with different nozzle designs had to be done, in order to find the one best suited.

To the left is shown the inner and outer nozzle. The setup is viewed from within the actual fountain, and the water is ejected in the room between the two nozzles.

Early prototype of inner nozzle.

Winning prototype. Stayed hollow the longest before collapsing

Failed prototype. Did not work as anticipated. Very short hollow jet.

Outer nozzle. Curved to streamline flow.

Solid vs. hollow laminar water jets

Solid laminar water jet. Frequently used in water fountains

Hollow laminar water jet. Replacement for solid jets. Our design.

Barrel for laminar water

A barrel like the one above is required in order to make the water calm and laminar, before it is ejected between the inner and outer nozzle .

Hollow water jets transport the enclosed air, and therefore require an air supply to avoid collapse.

This air supply is in the region of 0.2-1 liter per second, and can therefore be supplied by a very modest fan.

Application and future studies

The laminar hollow-jet technology can be used mainly on indoor fountains such as the one shown down in Lyngby Storcenter.

Although further study is required before laminar and hollow water jets are ready for commercial application, this project has shown, that there is a great potential for energy savings.